

Project Title	Blue-Cloud 2026: A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
Project Acronym	Blue-Cloud 2026
Project Number	101094227
Type of project	RIA – Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Starting date of Project	01 January 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	www.blue-cloud.org

D3.2 – Final release of open aggregated and harmonised EOVI datasets

Work Package	WP3 Developing and testing analytical Blue Cloud workbenches for generating highly qualified data collections (Essential Ocean Variables, EOVI)
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Peer reviewers	Dick Schaap (MARIS), Massimiliano Assante (CNR)
Version	V0.4
Due Date	30/06/2026
Submission Date	30/06/2026

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public
	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	11/06/2026	Marine Vernet (IFREMER)	Version for review by WP3 partners
0.2	22/06/2026	Marine Vernet (IFREMER)	Version for internal review
0.3	26/06/2026	Dick Schaap (MARIS), Massimiliano Assante (CNR)	Review
0.4	30/06/2026	Marine Vernet (IFREMER)	Final version for submission

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variable
GOOS	Global Ocean Observation System
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Services
WOD	World Ocean Database
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information System
EDITO	European Digital Twin of the Ocean
ODV	Ocean Data View
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean

Keywords

EOV; Workbenches; Physics; Eutrophication; Plankton; Habitat modelling; Quality control; Interoperability

Disclaimer

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094227. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides an inventory of the Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) and Essential Biodiversity Variable (EBV) datasets produced by the three analytical Workbenches developed within Work Package 3 of the Blue-Cloud2026 project. The Physics and Eutrophication Workbenches deliver complete, harmonised, deduplicated in situ observation datasets for chlorophyll, nutrients and oxygen and for temperature and salinity with additional quality control, integrating data from multiple European and global marine data infrastructures (SeaDataNet, EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service, World Ocean Database, and Argo). The Ecosystem Workbench delivers global spatial projections of plankton biodiversity and biomass produced through the CEPHALOPOD habitat modelling pipeline from heterogeneous biological observations including quantitative imaging, microscopy and metagenomics. They address GOOS biological EOVs related to plankton diversity and biomass. All EOv resulting datasets are available in the Blue-Cloud2026 catalogue (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/catalogue-bluecloud-cloud>) and will be published in open data repositories under open source licenses by August 2026. Plankton diversity and biomass EOv datasets are under embargo until peer-reviewed publication. All associated pipelines (Workbenches) are openly documented and available for reuse, ensuring the reproducibility and long-term sustainability of these products.

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1. EOv aggregated datasets

This deliverable provides an inventory of the Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) and Essential Biodiversity Variable (EBV) datasets produced within Work Package (WP) 3 of the Blue-Cloud2026 project, covering ocean physics, eutrophication and planktonic ecosystems.

The central objective of WP3 was to design, test and deploy analytical pipelines - referred to as “Workbenches” - for generating harmonised and highly qualified data collections for a selected set of essential variables. These Workbenches build on the Blue-Cloud2026 infrastructure and major data collections from multiple European and global marine data infrastructures such as SeaDataNet, EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service, World Ocean Database (WOD), EcoTaxa, EuroBIS, ENA, etc.

The Physics and Eutrophication Workbenches have delivered harmonised in situ observation datasets: multi-source measurements after semantic harmonisation, duplicate removal and quality control addressing physical and chemical EOvs as defined in the GOOS EOv framework. The Ecosystem Workbench has delivered global spatial projections of plankton biodiversity and biomass through statistical habitat modelling addressing both EOvs and EBVs from the GOOS and GEO BON framework.

The following sections present, for each Workbench, a summary of the data sources used, the produced datasets, the EOvs they address, and their access conditions.

1.1. Physical EOv datasets

The Physics Workbench (PWB) Lab targets two of the physical EOvs defined by the GOOS framework: ocean temperature and salinity. The PWB integrates in-situ profiles data from four major data infrastructures - SeaDataNet, Copernicus Marine Service in situ (CMEMS CORA), Argo and World Ocean Database (WOD) - into an aggregated, semantically harmonised, quality-controlled dataset. In addition to semantic harmonisation, a key methodological contribution is the additional quality control and duplicate detection across sources, and the integration of annotated metadata for provenance.

The resulting dataset covers the Mediterranean Sea (1950-2025) as a pilot region, and is delivered in **two formats** (*parquet*, *ODV spreadsheet* and *ODV collection*) and **two versions** respectively: one *cleaned* of duplicates, a second one *annotated* with duplicates and annotation for provenance traceability. It can be visualised and explored in the public dataspace of webODV (Figure 1) at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench/start-webodv>. The resulting dataset can be used for assimilation in ocean reanalysis, for deriving multi-year data products such as climate normals and ocean monitoring indicators.

Selected dataset: public -> PWB_EOVs_dataset_merged

The screenshot shows the webODV interface with a sidebar menu for 'public' datasets. The menu items are: BC26_workbenches, Eutrophication_workbench, Physics_workbench, EOVs_dataset (with sub-items: annotated, cleaned), Monoliths (with sub-items: ARGO, CORA_PR, CORA_TS, SEADATANET, WOD). The main content area contains introductory text about webODV services, a citation request, and a copyright notice.

Figure 1 – PWB EOvs dataset collections are available for exploration in webODV public dataspace

EOV addressed	Data name	file	Spatial coverage	Temporal coverage	Format	Dataset URL in Blue-Cloud	Dataset DOI
Subsurface temperature, Subsurface salinity	Physics Workbench EOv dataset		Mediterranean Sea	1950-2025	Parquet + JSON metadata, ODV	https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/physics_eovs_dataset	pending

Table 1 - Physical EOv dataset

All the EOv datasets produced through the PWB Lab are published in the Blue-Cloud catalogue under an open-source license ([CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)), and will be assigned a DOI in Zenodo by the end of August 2026.

They will then also be referenced in the EMODnet Physics catalogue, by which the EOv data set can also become available in the EDITO data lake.

Further information about the generated EOv dataset and the pipeline is available in the Physics Workbench Handbook: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/physics_workbench_lab_users_handbook

The Physics Workbench Lab is available here: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/physics-workbench>

All outputs from the Physics Workbench are available here : <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/physics-workbench/catalogue>

1.2. Eutrophication EOv datasets

The Eutrophication Workbench targets three biogeochemical EOvs and seven sub-variables defined by GOOS: oxygen (dissolved oxygen), ocean colour (chlorophyll-a), nutrients (nitrate, nitrite+nitrate, ammonium, phosphate, and silicate). These variables are central indicators of eutrophication status and ocean health, relevant to the MSFD among others. The Workbench integrates data from three data infrastructures - EMODnet Chemistry, CMEMS in-situ BGC, and WOD - applying semantic harmonisation, deduplication and annotation of the aggregated dataset. The resulting dataset in ODV or parquet format can be visualized and explored with WebODV at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/eutrophication-workbench/start-webodv>.

Gridded climatologies computed via DIVAnd constitute an additional downstream product, suitable for eutrophication indicator calculation in connection with the [Marine Environmental Indicator Vlab](#).

EOv addressed	Data file name	Spatial coverage	Time range	Format	Dataset URL	Dataset DOI
dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll -a, nutrients	Blue-Cloud2026 Global aggregated and harmonized eutrophication dataset	Global	1921-2025	Parquet, ODV	https://data.d4science.org/catalog/Eutrophication-Workbench/blue-cloud2026_global_aggregated_and_harmonized_eutrophication_dataset	pending

Table 2 - Chemical EOv dataset

All the EOv dataset produced through the Eutrophication Workbench are published in the [Blue-Cloud catalogue](#) under an open-source license ([CC-BY 4.0](#)), and will be assigned a DOI in Zenodo by the end of August 2026.

The dataset will then be referenced in the EMODnet Chemistry catalogue, by which the EOv dataset can also become available in the EDITO data lake.

Further information about the EOv datasets produced and the workflow is available in the Eutrophication Workbench Handbook: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Eutrophication-Workbench/eutrophication_workbench_users_handbook

The Eutrophication Workbench is available here: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/eutrophication-workbench>

All outputs from the Eutrophication Workbench are available here: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/eutrophication-workbench/catalogue>

1.3. Ecosystem EOv datasets

The Ecosystem Workbench targets EOvs and EBVs associated with phyto & zoo plankton biodiversity and biomass, addressing variables for which global, spatially continuous and methodologically consistent estimates have historically been lacking.

The integration of four complementary biological data types (species occurrences, abundance, biomass, metagenomic reads) within a unified modelling framework (CEPHALOPOD; Schickele et al. 2025) enables intercomparable global-scale biodiversity and biomass projections across species and observation methods based on the extrapolation of functional relationships between macroecological target variables and environmental predictor variables. Biological data sources are integrated from AtlantECO, GBIF and OBIS (both of which integrate outputs from EcoTaxa, and ELIXIR (MGnify)). Environmental predictor variables encompass all physical, biogeochemical and ecological EOvs known to affect plankton diversity and ecosystem composition. All delivered plankton diversity products are monthly climatologies, addressing the epipelagic layer (Schickele et al., in prep), while the plankton biomass products address 10 functional group for the epipelagic (0-200m) and 8 for the mesopelagic (200-500m) (Clerc et al., EcoEvoRxiv, 2026). Quality assessment of the model predictive performance is delivered alongside the dataset as a PDF report (Schickele et al. 2025). The resulting products can be visualized through the CEPHALOview application (<https://cephaloview.ethz.ch/>).

In addition to these global, gap-filled EOvs products, another part of the work to generate such products has consisted in the standardisation and annotation of biological input data itself through effort of Blue-Cloud2026 and sister projects partners responsible for the underlying data collections (AtlantECO and BiOcean5D; as well as ELIXIR's core developments). This data has been partly made available from the main international data repositories (GBIF and OBIS; MGnify via GBIF; Ecotaxa via EurOBIS), or through the data repository of ongoing and recently finished sister projects, as in the case of the AtlantECO data collection (which is currently being published at SEANOE), with the exception of the regridded and gap filled environmental predictor data that are currently available only through the Ecosystem Workbench

(whereas the underlying CMIP6 projections are publicly available through the CMIP project data repositories).

EOV targeted	Data file name	Spatial resolution	Time range	Format	Dataset URL in Blue-Cloud	Dataset DOI
plankton diversity	plankton_species_diversity_from_occurrence	1° x 1°	Monthly (12 months) + Annual average	NetCDF	https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Ecosystem-Workbench/ecosystem-workbench-harmonized-EOVs-and-EBVs-dataset	https://doi.org/10.17882/112686
plankton diversity	plankton_species_diversity_from_abundance	1° x 1°	Monthly (12 months) + Annual average	NetCDF	same as above	https://doi.org/10.17882/112686
plankton diversity	plankton_species_diversity_from_biomass	1° x 1°	Monthly (12 months) + Annual average	NetCDF	same as above	https://doi.org/10.17882/112686
plankton diversity	plankton_species_diversity_from_metagenomic	1° x 1°	Monthly (12 months) + Annual average	NetCDF	same as above	https://doi.org/10.17882/112686
plankton diversity	plankton_species_distribution_from_occurrence	1° x 1°	Monthly (12 months) + Annual average	NetCDF	same as above	https://doi.org/10.17882/112686
plankton biomass	Epipelagic_Zooplankton_PFT_Biomass	1° x 1°	Monthly (12 months) + Annual average	NetCDF	same as above	https://doi.org/10.17882/117486

plankton biomass	Mesopelagic_Zooplankton_PFT_Biomass	1° x 1°	Monthly (12 months) + Annual average	NetCDF	same as above	https://doi.org/10.17882/117486
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Table 3 - Biological EOv and EBv datasets

All the EOv & EBv datasets produced through the Ecosystem Workbench are published in the [SEANOE](#) data repository and referenced in the Blue-Cloud catalogue under open-source license ([CC-BY 4.0](#)):

- Schickele Alexandre, Clerc Corentin, Benedetti Fabio, Sonnet Virginie, Irisson Jean-Olivier, Pesant Stéphane, Vogt Meike (2026). Global maps of plankton biodiversity across observation types and diversity metrics in the epipelagic layer (0 - 50m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary environmental conditions (1990 - 2020) using an ensemble of habitat models. SEANOE. <https://doi.org/10.17882/112686>
- Clerc Corentin, Schickele Alexandre, Benedetti Fabio, Hofmann Elizondo Urs, Lunven Servane, Bader Ruby, Vivier Sébastien, Richardson Anthony J., Vogt Meike (2026). Global maps of zooplankton carbon biomass across plankton functional type (PFT) in the epipelagic layer (0 - 200m) and in the mesopelagic layer (200-500m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary environmental conditions (1990 - 2020) using an ensemble of habitat models. SEANOE. <https://doi.org/10.17882/117486>

As the datasets are the object of data publications (Schickele et al., in prep; Clerc et al., EcoEvoRxiv, 2026 - see References), they are under embargo until 31 December 2027, but the metadata is available on the dataset landing page, as well as contact to request access.

For the review, the datasets are available temporarily, upon request, on the following secured folder on the D4Science platform: <https://data.d4science.net/000cL>

Integration of the datasets into EMODnet Biology and EMODnet central catalogue or EDITO platform, upon relevance, will be further explored.

Further information about the EOv products generated and the Cephalopod pipeline is available on the dataset landing pages referenced in table 3 and in the Ecosystem Workbench Handbook: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Ecosystem-Workbench/ecosystem_workbench_user_handbook

The Ecosystem Workbench is available here: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/ecosystem-workbench>

All outputs from the Ecosystem Workbench are available here: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/ecosystem-workbench/catalogue>

2. Conclusion

The three Workbenches developed in WP3 of the Blue-Cloud2026 project have delivered open, aggregated, harmonised datasets for physical, biogeochemical and biological EOvs and EBVs, of interest to support ocean state assessment and understanding of oceanic systems, as well as well-documented analytical pipelines for generating these data sets.

The harmonised in situ observation datasets produced by the Physics and Eutrophication Workbenches bring together temperature and salinity, chlorophyll, nutrients and dissolved oxygen from multiple European data infrastructures (SeaDataNet, EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service, Argo and WOD) within a unified, semantically harmonised workflow. By addressing semantic and interoperability barriers between these sources, these datasets offer an additional level of consistency and traceability. The global projections of plankton diversity and biomass produced by the Ecosystem Workbench address the lack of spatially continuous biological EOv and EBv estimates at the global scale from multiple data types, allowing for comparisons across taxonomic groups and observation methods.

All datasets were designed for transparency, traceability and reproducibility. Documentation of source data provenance, semantic harmonisation and data annotation ensures the aggregated observation datasets from the Physics and Eutrophication Workbenches can be reproduced or adapted to user's needs. The explicit model quality flagging system and open availability of CEPHALOPOD allow users to assess the reliability of resulting EOvs and EBVs, and reproduce or extend the analysis to additional data types.

3. References

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